

Optimizing CNF Placement for Latency and Resource Efficiency in Multi-Cluster Cloud–Edge Federations

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ABSTRACT Service placement in current and next-generation mobile networks in emergency management is increasingly challenging due to resource-constrained edge clusters, where low latency and efficient workload distribution are critical. Traditional service placement strategies that rely solely on resource availability are no longer adequate. Modern deployments must address complex constraints, including end-to-end latency, system load distribution, and dynamic resource availability. In this paper, we propose a comprehensive architecture for service orchestration across multi-cluster Cloud-Edge environments, where independent clusters coordinate placement decisions through a federation layer. Our system is built on the Karmada federation control plane, which unifies heterogeneous cloud and edge clusters under a common framework to support optimal service placement. The core contribution of this work is a service placement solution integrated into a multi-cluster service management platform, supported by a decision-making module for service prioritization and optimal allocation. The decision process has two main components: (1) a multi-objective optimization model that balances CPU utilization and latency through a weighting mechanism, and (2) an Integer Linear Programming (ILP)-based model that prioritizes services and selectively discards requests when edge resources are constrained or system requirements cannot be met. A metric aggregator module is deployed via agents in each cluster and continuously monitors resource status to support placement decisions. Simulation results confirm that our approach ensures efficient resource usage and low latency, while maintaining low execution time even for large problem sizes. Additionally, we experimentally evaluate the proposed solution using our federated multi-cloud 5G testbed.

INDEX TERMS Federation, Multi-cluster orchestration, Service management, Edge computing, cloud-native, Optimization, Scheduling

I. INTRODUCTION

THE PLACEMENT of services across federated architectures with geographically distributed facilities has become a major challenge in 5G and beyond networks. These systems increasingly deploy applications closer to end-users (UEs) to meet the stringent demands of ultra-low latency and high computational efficiency [1]. Unlike traditional cloud environments that rely on centralized orchestration, next-generation architectures are shifting toward geographically distributed edge clusters with heterogeneous resource capacities and latency profiles [2], [3]. In such settings, service placement decisions must consider not only resource

availability but also critical performance constraints such as end-to-end delay, workload balancing, and inter-cluster coordination.

Federated orchestration has emerged as a practical response to the growing complexity of service deployment in federated environments [4]. In such a setup, each cluster is managed independently but still contributes to a shared service infrastructure. Placement decisions in this context must consider global factors (such as latency requirements and overall system load) while also navigating challenges like limited visibility across domains, administrative boundaries, and control-plane communication overhead. To be

effective, placement decisions must be computed globally [5], while also being aware of these local limitations. As a result, centralized scheduling mechanisms, which are often designed to provide a holistic view of the system, remain valuable due to their ability to optimize resource allocation globally, enforce consistent policies, and handle complex scheduling constraints such as affinity/anti-affinity rules and multi-resource requirements. These capabilities are particularly beneficial in environments where decentralized components offer only partial observability of system state. In such contexts, centralized schedulers must still make timely and effective decisions based on incomplete or fragmented information, while interacting with distributed elements of the system. The importance of solving this challenge is especially evident in latency-sensitive verticals such as autonomous driving, emergency services, and remote healthcare, which illustrate the kinds of applications that can suffer from poor placement decisions. While our approach is generally applicable, these examples highlight the critical need for efficient orchestration in federated environments.

To support such complex placement decisions, it is essential to rely on mathematical formulation that captures both system constraints and optimization goals. Integer Linear Programming (ILP) offers a suitable method in this context, as it enables the problem to be expressed using formal constraints and decision variables. In a service placement scenario, ILP makes it possible to model how services are assigned to clusters based on relevant system limits, like available CPU capacity and latency requirements. However, placement in federated (multi-cluster) environments rarely involves a single objective. Minimizing service latency and balancing computational loads across clusters are both critical for maintaining system performance and avoiding resource saturation. Since these objectives often conflict, they must be addressed jointly. To do so, we adopt a multi-objective optimization (MOO) formulation [6], where latency and load balancing are combined in a single objective function using a weighted approach. This allows the placement strategy to be adapted to different service profiles or runtime conditions, offering a more flexible and responsive placement process.

Although orchestration platforms such as Kubernetes and Karmada [7] provide extensibility through plugins and policy modules, they do not natively support latency-aware optimization or service prioritization under tight constraints. Most existing schedulers rely on heuristics or local metrics, which makes them insufficient for multi-cluster scenarios where global visibility and coordinated decisions are essential. This gap motivates the development of an external, optimizer-driven architecture that integrates with, but extends beyond, the capabilities of existing control planes.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of constrained service placement in federated environments, we introduce a placement strategy tailored for multi-cluster architecture. This work builds upon our earlier study [8] with several architectural and algorithmic enhancements. First, we

generalize the service placement problem into a multi-objective optimization framework that jointly considers computational load and end-to-end latency, enabling a better trade-off between these competing goals. Unlike our previous single-objective approach, this dual-objective formulation improves both resource utilization and service responsiveness. Second, we introduced an optimal pre-deployment service selection strategy rather than relying on simple heuristics or removing services one by one based solely on resource demands, our method identifies the minimal subset of services that must be discarded to restore feasibility when the system is overloaded or hard constraints cannot be met. Beyond the algorithmic advances, we implement and evaluate the proposed architecture on a real experimental testbed. The results confirm that the system operates modularly and efficiently in practical deployments. Finally, we present an extensive benchmarking study that analyzes system behavior under varying load and latency conditions, and we compare our method against several baseline placement strategies.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews relevant works on service placement, focusing on both theoretical models and practical implementations, especially within Kubernetes-based service management and orchestration systems. Sections III and IV detail our proposed architecture, including its mathematical formulation and optimization design. Section V presents simulation results and validation on a real-world testbed. The discussion is presented in Section VI, and finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORKS

ILP has been widely applied in the field of service placement, particularly for solving the Virtual Network Function Placement and Chaining (VNF-PC) problem under various optimization objectives [9], [10], [11]. For instance, the authors in [9] proposed an ILP model to minimize end-to-end latency in 5G networks by allocating Service Function Chains (SFCs) across distributed data centers, achieving latency improvements at the cost of computational scalability. Similarly, the study in [12] introduced an ILP model to optimize VNF placement through different reconfiguration strategies, including resizing instances, rerouting traffic, and relocating VNFs, with the goal of maximizing provider profit while meeting Quality of Service (QoS) constraints. Other ILP-based approaches have tackled specific problems. For example, [13] focused on optimizing throughput for VNF placement under time-varying workloads. Although formulated as an ILP, the authors also proposed a heuristic to improve scalability for larger network sizes. In [14], the focus shifted to minimizing energy consumption when deploying parallelized SFCs (PSFCs), while ensuring end-to-end delay requirements and mitigating resource interference. To overcome scalability limitations, a dedicated heuristic called EPSFC was introduced. ILP models have also been adopted in the domain-specific

applications; for instance, [15] presented an ILP approach for jointly optimizing the placement and scheduling of VNFs in a remote robotic surgery system, satisfying stringent latency and reliability constraints while minimizing deployment costs. Despite their optimality, ILP-based solutions often suffer from long runtimes and limited scalability, especially as network size and service complexity increase. These drawbacks have motivated the deployment of hybrid and heuristic approaches.

To address the computational complexity, several works have extended ILP to Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP), which supports more flexible modeling of both discrete and continuous variables. In [16], a MILP model was developed for dynamic container placement in mobile fog-cloud environments. The model aimed to maximize the workload processing while minimizing migration costs and latency, using a sequential optimization strategy to balance placement quality against computational efficiency. Similarly, [17] proposed a MILP formulation for network-aware scheduling of microservices in edge-cloud environments. By combining graph partitioning with MILP-based refinement, the approach achieved latency-aware placement while adhering to locality and resource constraints. These studies demonstrate that MILP models can better capture real-world deployment factors such as mobility and topology, though runtime challenges persist in large-scale scenarios.

Traditional VNFs were often built by moving legacy software into large virtual machines without redesigning. This made them hard to scale, resource-heavy, and difficult to manage. As a result, they are less suitable for modern use cases like 5G and edge computing [18]. With the transition toward microservice-oriented and container-based architectures, however, this focus is shifting toward container orchestration systems like Kubernetes. Unlike the earlier VM-centric placement models, Kubernetes scheduling operates at a much finer level, assigning pod and containers rather than full virtual machines. This finer granularity introduces additional considerations, such as optimizing pods placement and communication, supporting the co-placement of related services, and responding to fluctuating workloads. As a result, ongoing research efforts are increasingly focused on enhancing Kubernetes scheduling to be network-aware and better suited for NFV scenarios and latency-sensitive deployments.

In this context, authors of [19] proposed a network-aware scheduling framework for Kubernetes that incorporates latency and bandwidth constraints into placement decisions. Their framework extends the default Kubernetes (K8s) scheduler with custom plugins that use real-time network topology data to improve pod placement. A MILP model was also included as a benchmark to assess the plugin's performance. Similarly, [20] developed an orchestration framework that integrates metaheuristic algorithms with an ILP-based scheduler to optimize Kubernetes placement across geographically distributed regions. They specifically

targeted batch workloads in Apache Spark, aiming to reduce network latency and improve resource utilization across edge-cloud clusters. In the context of network slicing, the work in [21] introduced a Kubernetes scheduler that employs a Genetic Algorithm (GA) to manage the deployment of complete network slices as indivisible units. Unlike conventional schedulers that handle pods individually, their "closed box" approach ensures that either all pods in a slice are placed together or none are deployed, thereby improving both resource efficiency and slice acceptance rates.

Recent advances in network service orchestration have introduced a range of placement strategies spanning analytical modeling, optimization, and AI/ML-based approaches. These learning-based methods often aim to improve scalability and adaptability, particularly in complex or highly variable network settings, such as non-terrestrial networks (NTNs), multi-access edge computing (MEC), or 5G/6G systems. Authors in [22] analyze the properties of microservice applications that can affect the ability of a placement strategy to deploy microservices in edge data centers to reduce the average user delay. The analysis is supported by a new analytical model of delay and a new placement strategy, called Path Adding Microservice Placement (PAMP), which considers key aspects of the application, and of the supporting computing and network systems.

In parallel, numerous studies have explored AI/ML-based techniques to address dynamic orchestration challenges. For instance, the work in [23] introduces a proactive container network function (CNF) placement framework in non-terrestrial networks (NTNs) by utilizing ML to forecast container resource usage and enable demand-aware orchestration. Similarly, [24] proposes a closed-loop service management system using AI-driven self-monitoring, self-configuration, and self-optimization models, which demonstrates the potential of intelligent automation in maintaining service quality in cloud-native infrastructures.

Reinforcement learning (RL) has been widely applied to placement and caching problems as well. In [25], a deep RL-based approach is proposed for parallel service function chain (SFC) caching, aiming to reduce latency and cold-start issues through more efficient runtime image placement. The work in [26] formulates the VNF placement problem as a constrained optimization task and solves it using Neural Combinatorial Optimization (NCO) combined with Reward Constrained Policy Optimization (RCPO), enabling the system to make resource-aware decisions while minimizing network fragmentation. Likewise, [27] applies RL techniques such as AVP-Q and AVP-DQN within a Markov Decision Process (MDP) framework to improve VNF placement in 5G industrial scenarios, focusing on delay reduction and reliable performance under variable wireless conditions.

Further developments also explore ML-based placement and orchestration strategies focused on improving flexibility, scalability, and resource efficiency. For instance, [28] proposes a learning-based approach for service function

chain (SFC) placement in edge environments, which aims to maximize long-term performance while managing system complexity. In [29], the authors introduce a dynamic scaling framework for containerized network functions, targeting improved energy efficiency and reduced overprovisioning. Additionally, [30] presents an architectural and scheduling approach designed to meet low-latency orchestration requirements in B5G/6G networks, demonstrating performance improvements over commonly used platforms like Kubernetes and Docker Swarm.

In summary, the literature demonstrates a wide range of placement strategies, from ILP and MILP formulations that support fine-grained optimization under multiple constraints to learning-based approaches that enable adaptive, data-driven orchestration in dynamic environments. Building on these efforts, our work focuses on a service placement model for latency-sensitive and resource-constrained scenarios in multi-cluster edge-cloud environments. The model is implemented modularly within a centralized control plane (Karmada) that enables the policy-driven placement across heterogeneous clusters with practical deployment. Compared to prior works such as [19] and [20], which make online, per-pod decisions using heuristic or metaheuristic approach, our work extends the optimization scope and decision process. First, we integrate a multi-objective MILP directly into the live placement process, so latency and cluster CPU load are optimized together for all services in a batch. Second, we add an optimal solution that prioritize critical services for deployment by removing only the smallest set of low-priority ones when resources are tight. Third, while prior works measure performance mainly in terms of request latency or scheduling quality, we focus on service instantiation time, which is key for quickly deploying complex workloads in multi-cluster edge-cloud environments.

III. EXTENDED FEDERATION ARCHITECTURE

FIGURE 1 illustrates the high-level architecture of the proposed federated service management system, which enables service orchestration across heterogeneous cloud and edge clusters in a multi-cluster environment. This architecture is designed to support low-latency and resource-efficient service placement through centralized decision-making, while maintaining observability across distributed infrastructure. At its core is the Federated Control Plane, built on Karmada, which centrally manages service deployments across all participating clusters. These clusters include both cloud and edge environments, where services are instantiated. End devices (e.g., laptops and mobile phones) connect to these services via Wireless LANs (WLANs). To ensure performance, Monitoring Agents are deployed within the clusters to collect telemetry data, such as resource utilization and network statistics. This data is sent to a central Metric Aggregator, which processes and consolidates the metrics. The aggregated data then feeds into the Optimizer & Decision Maker, the intelligence of the system responsible

FIGURE 1. High-level architecture overview of the federated service management system.

FIGURE 2. Interaction diagram of core modules supporting service placement.

for calculating optimal service placements. The entire process is managed by the Federated Service Manager, which orchestrates the deployment and lifecycle of services across the distributed clusters based on the optimizer’s decisions and monitored metrics like end-to-end (e2e) latency. FIGURE 2 presents a detailed view of the internal architecture and operational workflow of the federated service orchestrator.

The process begins when a user or external system submits a batch of service deployment requests to the Federation API Server, which serves as the primary entry point for all operations (FIGURE 2, top-left). Each request includes deployment specifications in the form of policies and is handled as part of a batch of services (denoted as s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n).

Once received, the deployment request is forwarded to the service queue, through a two-stages scheduling pipeline: 1) Filtering, where clusters are shortlisted based on static criteria such as affinity policies, taint tolerances, and resource eligibility, and 2) Scoring, where dynamic metrics are evaluated to rank candidate clusters. This preliminary process ensures that only clusters meeting both policy and resource

TABLE 1. Notation.

Symbol	Description
G	Graph representing clusters C and nodes N .
B	A batch of services S , where each s represents a complete service package.
n_c	Where c denotes a given cluster and n denotes node within the cluster c .
i, j	Cluster identifier.
cpu_{nc}	Total Available CPU resources on node n or cluster c .
cpu_s	Minimum CPU required for service s .
l_c	End-to-end latency between the user and cluster c
l_m	Latency requirement of microservice $m \in M_s$
l_s	Service-level latency requirement for service s
ω	Weight assigned to a factor in the problem formulation.
$x_{s,c}$	Decision variable. If it is 1 means service s is deployed in cluster c .
y_s	Decision variable. If 1 service should be kept in queue.
id_s	Identifier number of service s .
$O_{c/s}$	The object presents a snapshot of the cluster or service in system.
s_d	Service s demand
C_d	Clusters demand
S'	A set of services excluding S or s .

thresholds are considered for placement. In the current implementation, the focus is on the Filtering phase, and the Scoring mechanisms are not yet included. After this initial filtering, the remaining clusters and service requests are passed to the Cluster Resource Plugin, which bridges the internal scheduler and the external optimizer. This plugin gathers runtime metrics (CPU, latency) from the Metric Aggregator and constructs an optimization problem that is sent to the Optimizer Module.

The Optimizer and Decision-Maker is composed of three integrated sub-components: *i) A Web interface*: serves as the entry point to open communication with the Optimizer and allows it to be exposed and responsive to incoming requests.

This allows the Optimizer to receive input data from the plugin and preprocess the parameters required for the problem-solving phase. *ii) ILP Solver*: accommodates the formulated optimization model and computes solutions that satisfy multi-objective placement constraints. It solves the placement problem for a batch of services by minimizing end-to-end latency and reducing resource utilization, which ensures that service-specific performance requirements are met. The mathematical formulation of the ILP model is implemented within this module and is described in detail in the next section. *iii) Priority-Aware Planer (PAP)*: This module is integrated within the optimizer and is designed to handle challenging scenarios where resource constraints or strict requirements make service placement difficult or infeasible using standard methods. It evaluates the priority of each incoming service request in comparison to other services in the batch. This evaluation considers both predefined priority levels and factors, such as the need to meet latency constraints, particularly for services intended to run on edge clusters. To this, it retrieves real-time resource usage and performance metrics from the Monitoring Module,

and based on this information, it filters out a set of lower-priority services whose removal would make enough capacity to enable the placement of critical services.

Once a valid placement decision is made, the solution is returned to the federation layer. After the scheduler makes a placement decision, a Binding object is generated that maps the workload to the chosen clusters. The Controllers then take the binding information and generate the appropriate Deployment Manifests, propagating them to the relevant Cluster Members. Within each cluster, the local Kubernetes API Server, Scheduler, and Kubelet Agent work together to launch and manage the deployed service pods.

$$\cup_{c \in C} N_c = N \text{ and } N_i \cap N_j = \emptyset \text{ for all } i \neq j \quad (1)$$

$$cpu_c = \sum_{n \in N_c} cpu_n \quad \forall c \in C \quad (2)$$

$$cpu_s = \sum_{m \in M_s} cpu_m \quad \forall s \in S \quad (3)$$

$$l_s = \min_{m \in M_s} l_m \quad \forall s \in S \quad (4)$$

The Metric Aggregator in FIGURE 1 continuously collects telemetry data such as CPU load and per-packet network latency from all participating Cloud/Edge Clusters through its Monitoring agent. After the scheduling and optimization are complete, the system hands over placement decisions to a set of dedicated Karmada controllers, which 1) translate the placement plan into actual resource definitions, 2) propagate these definitions to the selected clusters to trigger deployment.

IV. ALGORITHMIC AND MATHEMATICAL FRAMEWORK

This section presents the models and algorithms supporting our proposed service placement strategy, which integrates an optimization-based resource allocation model with a robust decision-making mechanism. The approach aims to effectively distribute services across clusters while preserving feasibility, even when system constraints, such as high resource utilization, would otherwise prevent a valid placement solution. To achieve this, the methodology is structured into two elements: (i) the problem formulation, which defines the optimization objective and constraints; and (ii) the service removal strategy, which identifies services to exclude when saturation prevents feasible deployment. Also, we present the service placement process, which determines how services are assigned to available clusters.

A. SYSTEM MODEL AND FORMULA

We formulate the service placement problem as a constrained, multi-objective optimization task that seeks to minimize CPU load imbalance and total service latency while satisfying service-specific constraints. This formulation extends previous work [8] by incorporating both CPU and latency considerations as co-primary objectives. At its core, the service placement challenge is modeled as a multi-objective optimization problem that aims to balance computational resource utilization while adhering

to latency constraints. The goal is to avoid overloading any single resource unit while keeping overall latency as low as possible within the acceptable range. This multi-objective optimization problem is naturally linked to the Pareto efficiency concept, where improving one objective may come at the cost of the other. Therefore, we introduce a trade-off mechanism to identify placements that achieve an optimal balance between the two.

The infrastructure is modeled as a graph $G = (C, N)$ where C is the set of clusters, and N is the set of computing nodes. Each cluster $c \in C$ contains a subset of nodes, denoted as $N_c \subseteq N$ which means that every node in the system belongs to one cluster (see Equation (1)). Each computing node $n \in N$ has an associated CPU capacity cpu_n , and the total available CPU

$$\sum_{c \in C} x_{s,c} = 1 \quad \forall s \in S \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{s \in S} cpu_s \cdot x_{s,c} \leq cpu_c \quad \forall c \in C \quad (6)$$

$$l_c \cdot x_{s,c} \leq l_s \quad \forall s \in S \text{ and } c \in C \quad (7)$$

$$\min \left(\omega_{cpu} \cdot \max_{c \in C} \sum_{s \in S} cpu_s \cdot x_{s,c} + \omega_{lat} \cdot \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{c \in C} l_c \cdot x_{s,c} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$\omega_s = g(l_s, cpu_s) \quad (9)$$

capacity of a cluster is defined as the sum of the capacities of its nodes (Equation (2)). Clusters also exhibit a latency parameter l_c , representing the cumulative network and processing delay within the cluster and its communication delay to the UE.

Incoming service requests arrive in batches of size $B=|S|$ where S is the set of services in batch B . Each service $s \in S$ comprises a set of microservices M_s , with an aggregated CPU demand (Equation (3)). Latency requirements are defined per service based on the most restrictive requirement, as the minimum latency constraint, among its microservices (Equation (4)). A binary decision variable $x_{s,c}$ indicates whether service s is assigned to cluster c . Equation (5) assures that each service must be placed in exactly one cluster. Equation (6) makes sure that no cluster is overloaded and placement must adhere to cluster capacity constraints. Additionally, Equation (7) checks that service s may only be placed in cluster that latency does not exceed its tolerable bound.

The objective in Equation (8) seeks to minimize both the peak CPU load across clusters and the total experienced latency. And finally, as is shown in Equation (9), the weights can be adapted on a per-service basis to reflect specific performance priorities. A generalized function $g(\cdot)$ is introduced to compute service-specific weights ω_s as a function of latency and CPU demand.

B. SERVICE REMOVAL STRATEGY

In highly constrained environments, the optimization solver may fail to determine a feasible allocation for the full batch

of services. This may result either from hard constraint violations (e.g., a service's latency exceeds that of all clusters), or from infeasibility caused by aggregate demand exceeding available capacity. To address this, we propose a removal mechanism that eliminates the minimal number of services necessary to restore feasibility before any deployment occurs.

Let $y_s \in \{0,1\}$ be a binary variable indicating whether service s is removed from the current batch. The objective in Equation (10) is to minimize the number of removals. Equation (11) ensures that each service is either placed in a cluster or removed, but not both.

$$\min \sum_{s \in S} y_s \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{c \in C} x_{s,c} + y_s = 1, \quad \forall s \in S \quad (11)$$

The combined model is solved iteratively: if a valid placement is not found, the optimization is re-executed with a revised service set, omitting the lowest-priority services based on a removal policy (e.g., weighted by resource demand and latency criticality). This process continues until feasibility is achieved and only then is the resulting plan applied to deploy the services.

The priority-based removal strategy was selected to ensure that mission-critical services (e.g., in emergency management or remote healthcare) are preserved when resources are constrained. Its main advantage is predictable behavior under contention, as it discards only lower-priority requests to maintain the operation of high-priority ones. The main drawback is the possible starvation of low-priority services in prolonged overload situations, and the challenge of defining an effective and fair priority scheme. Compared with simpler strategies such as FIFO or dropping the largest service first, our ILP-based approach considers both priority and feasibility, removing the minimal set of low-priority services needed to restore capacity, thus minimizing the impact on high-priority workloads.

C. PLACEMENT ALGORITHM DESIGN

In the following section, we present the algorithms that support the service placement workflow within the federation environment. The discussion here is closely linked to the experimental platform. The architecture is illustrated in FIGURE 2, and the workflow is described in Algorithm 1. The placement logic is encapsulated in a custom plugin developed using the FilterPlugin interface of the underlying federation scheduler. This plugin serves as an integration point between the scheduler and the external ILP-based optimization engine. The execution flow of the placement process is detailed in Algorithm 1 which is divided into three parts: (i) and (ii) the internal execution within the scheduler, responsible for collecting resource information and interacting with the optimizer, and (iii) the external logic executed by the optimizer, where the placement decision is computed. In lines 1-8, a batch of service requests is received, and the scheduler invokes the plugin iteratively for

Algorithm 1**i) Cluster resource plugin integration with the federation system****Input:** $framework, O_C$ **Output:** $framework^*$

```

1  $service\ placement \leftarrow \{\}$ 
2  $service\ placement \leftarrow newFilterPlugin()$ 
3 for  $c^* \in C$  do
4    $match \leftarrow Cluster\ Match(c^*, O_C)$ 
5   if  $match = True$  then
6     return Success
7   ...else continue

```

ii) Main cluster selector function**Input:** c^*, O_C, O_S **Output:** $true/false$

```

8  $id_s, S_d \leftarrow O_S$ 
9 for  $c \in O_C$  do
10   $N \leftarrow c.clientset.nodes()$ 
11   $S' \leftarrow c.clientset.service()$ 
12  for  $n \in N$  do
13     $c_{cpu} \leftarrow n.status.cpu().val()$ 
14    for  $s' \in S'$  do
15      if  $s'.node\ name = n.name$  do
16         $cpu \leftarrow s'.requests.cpu()$ 
17         $c_{cpu} \leftarrow c_{cpu} - cpu$ 
18  for  $c \in O_C$  do
19     $c_l \leftarrow HTTP.post(ip, c)$ 
20     $C_d \leftarrow merge\ all\ c_{cpu}, c_l$ 
21  struct  $profile \leftarrow id_s, S_d, C_d$ 
22   $c_{target} \leftarrow HTTP.post(ip, profile)$ 
23  if  $c_{target} = c^*$  then
24    return true
25  else return false

```

iii) Optimizer and decision maker**Input:** $request$ **Output:** c_{target}

```

26  $id \leftarrow request.id$ 
27 if  $id = 1$  then
28   $S_{pend} \leftarrow filter\ any\ s' \in S\ not\ meet\ constraints$ 
29  while True do
30     $M' \leftarrow Model()$ 
31     $M' \leftarrow add\ constrains\ due\ to\ eq.\ (4), (6), (7), (8)$ 
32     $solution \leftarrow minimize\ M'$ 
33    if not  $solution$  do
34       $M'' \leftarrow Model()$ 
35       $S_{pend} \leftarrow minimize\ M''$ 
36      update  $S$ 
37      else break
38  else
39     $c_{target} \leftarrow solution(id)$ 
40  return  $c_{target}$ 

```

each cluster. If a cluster meets initial filtering criteria, it is marked as a candidate for hosting the service. According to lines 9-25, the plugin collects runtime metrics such as available CPU and latency from an external metrics aggregator. These metrics, along with the service batch description, are used to formulate the optimization query.

Then upon receiving the query, based on lines 26-40, the optimization engine solves the placement problem. If the solver identifies a feasible mapping, the plugin returns the appropriate cluster for each service. In case of infeasibility, a removal routine is triggered, and the optimization is re-attempted.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we present a detailed analysis of the outcomes produced by our ILP-based algorithm for optimal service placement among the member clusters in the federation environment.

A. SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

The experiments were conducted using CPLEX (22.1.1) [31] as the solver and Python (version 3.9) for implementation. The simulations were run on a system equipped with 12 CPU cores and operating on Windows 10. In this work, CPU resources are measured in millicores (m), as this aligns with how cluster orchestrators like Kubernetes, represent CPU allocation. To maintain consistency between Python-based simulator and the actual execution environment, we adopted the same unit of measurement. For the simulation configuration, we considered homogeneous CPU demands, where each cluster had a fixed CPU capacity of 5000m. The CPU requirements for service placement were categorized into six different demand levels and are designed to show the varying levels of computational demand. Each service request was assigned a CPU demand that was randomly generated from a predefined range, where the lower bound was consistently set at 100m, while the upper bound varied across different levels up to 7000m. The upper bound values increased and covered a spectrum from low-demand CPU needs to highly intensive services requiring several thousand millicores. The latency configuration was structured such that each cluster had a fixed latency to the master node, with values set at 10 ms, 20 ms, and 50 ms. The requested service latencies were generated uniformly within predefined ranges, where the minimum latency was fixed at 1 ms, and the maximum latency increased progressively up to 200 ms over several intervals to simulate increasing service latency demands.

It is important to note that the same ILP solver and service removal logic used in the simulation is also deployed in the real testbed. The optimizer behavior is consistent across both environments. Simulations model latency using fixed RTT values and evaluate placement decisions without running actual service traffic. This setup enables controlled, scalable analysis of placement behavior under varying load conditions.

B. STRATEGIES FOR BALANCING CPU AND LATENCY FACTORS

As discussed in Section IV, effective balancing between CPU usage and latency under optimization requires a weighting parameter (ω), due to their differing units and

FIGURE 3. Allocated latency under different CPU ranges: (a) CPU range 1, (b) CPU range 3.

fluctuating scales. In this section, we examine three adaptive weighting (*i-iii*) approaches that address this challenge from distinct perspectives to make them well-suited for dynamic optimization problems where resource demands vary over time. (i) *Variance Scaling (SD)*¹: This statistically grounded method uses the standard deviation of CPU and latency values as scaling factors, allowing each metric to be weighted in proportion to its variability and mitigating dominance by any single factor. (ii) *Maximum-Minimum normalization (Max-Min)*: This approach rescales CPU and latency values to a fixed [0,1] range, preserving their relative differences while minimizing the impact of extreme values. (iii) *Maximum normalization (Max)*: A simpler method that normalizes each metric by its maximum value, focusing on absolute dominance without considering the full range. Additionally, we introduce three fixed-weight strategies as baselines to illustrate the limitations of static objective weighting and to emphasize the advantages of adaptive methods. (iv) *B-L (Latency-Biased)*: Assigns full weight to latency and none to CPU. (v) *B-C (CPU-Biased)*: Assigns full weight to CPU and none to latency. (vi) *B-B (Balanced)*: Allocates equal weight (0.5) to both CPU and latency.

C. ANALYSIS OF LATENCY ALLOCATION ACROSS DIFFERENT CPU LOAD CONDITIONS

We begin by evaluating the weighting methods used to configure Equation (9). FIGURE 3 presents the average allocated latency, the experienced latency, resulting from service to cluster assignments across all the repetitions as a function of latency requests under two CPU load conditions. FIGURE 3(a) shows the results for a low-load range (1),

¹“SD” stands for “Standard Deviation.”

FIGURE 4. Trade-off between average allocated latency (bars) and maximum allocated CPU load (lines) under two CPU ranges: (a) CPU range 1, (b) CPU range 3.

while FIGURE 3(b) illustrates the case of a higher-load range (3). Since the objective is to minimize aggregated latency across assigned clusters, lower curves in the figure reflect better optimization performance.

Under CPU range (1), the B-L approach, which optimizes solely for latency, consistently achieves the lowest latency allocation across all request levels and thus serves as a performance reference. However, this method disregards CPU balancing and may lead to resource congestion under higher loads. The B-C approach, which prioritizes CPU utilization, yields the highest latency due to more distributed but no latency-efficient service placement. The B-B strategy, assigning equal weights to CPU and latency, results in intermediate latency values, representing a trade-off between latency optimization and CPU load balancing. The scaling-based methods, SD, Max-Min, and Max, demonstrate more moderate latency outcomes. Notably, under low CPU load (range 1), the Max method outperforms SD and Max-Min in latency reduction. However, under higher CPU load (range 3), increasing CPU constraints limit the flexibility of all methods, leading to reduced service allocation and consequently lower average allocated latency. In this setting, the performance of scaling approaches converges toward that of the B-L strategy, which is similarly constrained by CPU limitations and cannot maintain its latency advantage as in the unconstrained case.

FIGURE 4 presents the trade-off between service latency and CPU load for the two CPU utilization ranges considered in the study. In both subplots, the bar series reports the average allocated latency for successfully deployed services, while the line series shows the maximum allocated CPU load among all clusters. For the low utilization range (1) in FIGURE 4(a), most strategies achieve relatively low CPU load but differ significantly in latency performance. In this scenario, our proposed strategy maintains competitive

FIGURE 5. Allocated latency comparison to other approaches.

latency while avoiding excessive concentration of workload on a single cluster. In the medium utilization range (3) in FIGURE 4(b), the differences become more pronounced: strategies that minimize latency without considering load balancing (e.g., B-L, Balanced) tend to drive CPU usage close to saturation in certain clusters, while load-aware strategies (e.g., Max-Min, SD) reduce peak CPU load at the expense of slightly higher latency. These results highlight the importance of jointly evaluating latency and load metrics, as focusing on a single objective can lead to undesirable trade-offs in federated multi-cluster environments.

D. ANALYSIS OF LATENCY ALLOCATION COMPARING DIFFERENT STANDARD TECHNIQUES

In this section, we assess the effectiveness of our ILP-based solution in comparison to two baseline methods: a standard Load Balancer and the First Fit (greedy) algorithm, focusing on allocated latency. The Load Balancer emphasizes even CPU load distribution across clusters to avoid overload, but it does not explicitly aim to minimize latency. In contrast, the First Fit algorithm disregards CPU balancing and instead places services in the nearest available cluster, seeking to minimize latency.

Both approaches respect CPU and latency constraints during placement and prioritize latency-sensitive requests by sorting each batch accordingly. To assess algorithmic scalability and performance under load, the evaluation includes stress-test scenarios involving large service request batches, exceeding typical edge volumes but suitable for analyzing placement behavior under high-demand conditions.

FIGURE 5 illustrates the average allocated latency as a function of the number of service requests, with batch sizes ranging from 10 to 240 services. Across most request sizes, the ILP approach maintains a balanced latency allocation between the results of First Fit and Load Balancer. For request sizes between 10 and 200, First Fit achieves the lowest latency due to its greedy strategy; however for larger batches (above 240 services), First Fit’s result increases beyond that of ILP, showing that its uncoordinated allocation leads to congestion in frequently used clusters. The Load Balancer consistently results in the highest latency across all batch sizes, which aligns with its objective of CPU load distribution rather than latency minimization. These results

FIGURE 6. Ratio of Not allocated service under two CPU ranges: (a) CPU range 3, and (b) CPU range 5.

suggest that when latency reduction is critical, particularly in large-scale deployments, the ILP approach offers the most effective balance.

E. ANALYSIS OF SERVICE ALLOCATION ACROSS LATENCY REQUESTS

To analyze the interaction between latency and CPU constraints in service placement, we introduce the Not Allocated Service Ratio metric, which quantifies the fraction of services that could not be placed due to either CPU limitations or unmet latency requirements. This metric reflects the system’s capacity to fulfill service requests under constrained resources. FIGURE 6 shows the average ratio of unallocated services across varying latency requests under two CPU load conditions, FIGURE 6(a) shows ranges 3 and FIGURE 6(b) shows range 5, evaluated across ILP (Section III), SD, Max-Min, and Max scaling strategies. Scaling factors are applied during the service removal phase, assigning scores based on both CPU and latency requirements. Across all methods, unallocated services decrease as latency requests become more relaxed, indicating easier allocation under looser constraints. This trend holds in both CPU ranges, although a higher CPU load results in a higher unallocated ratio.

Initially, all methods exhibit a similar ratio, suggesting that latency constraints, not the removal strategy, are the dominant limiting factor at low request levels. As latency requests increase, the impact of each strategy becomes clearer. Among the methods, ILP consistently yields the lowest unallocated ratio, indicating more effective resource utilization. While SD and Max-Min show comparable trends, they tend to result in a slightly higher unallocated ratio in mid-range latency scenarios compared to the Max scaling strategy.

FIGURE 7. Ratio of Not allocated service (a) average for all CPU ranges and (b) maximum for all CPU ranges.

F. ANALYSIS OF SERVICE ALLOCATION ACROSS CPU LOAD LEVELS

As more completed results, the heatmap in FIGURE 7 illustrates the average (FIGURE 7(a)) and maximum (FIGURE 7(b)) unallocated service ratio for all latency requests under varying CPU load conditions.

For low CPU load conditions (range 1 to 3), all strategies perform almost identically. This suggests that in low CPU loaded scenarios, the impact of the removal strategy is minimal. As CPU load increases (range 4 to 6), the differences between the strategies become more pronounced. In range (4), ILP achieves the lowest average ~ 0.34 and maximum ~ 0.54 , while other methods, particularly SD and Max-Min, result in slightly higher ratio. This indicates that ILP provides a better allocation strategy in moderate CPU load scenarios. For higher CPU load conditions (range 5 and 6), all strategies experience a significant increase in unallocated ratios, which is caused by the system’s inability to accommodate all demands. ILP consistently maintains lower values compared to others, in these two loads as well.

G. ANALYSIS OF MAXIMUM LOAD ACROSS DIFFERENT CPU LOAD RANGES

This section focuses on minimizing maximum cluster load, one of the key objectives. FIGURE 8(a) shows the average maximum load across all latency requests and repetitions under varying CPU loads. In prior work [8], a CPU-only objective performs better than a standard load balancer (LB), especially under high load. As expected, B-L (Latency-Biased) results in the highest maximum loads, while L-C (CPU-Biased) achieves the lowest across all ranges. In low to medium CPU loads (ranges 1-3), scaling methods

FIGURE 8. (a) Maximum CPU allocation, (b) max-to-mean ratio.

differ noticeably from L-C, with Max scaling showing a significant deviation (e.g., ~ 71.66 in range 1). However, as CPU load increases (ranges 4-6), the performance gap narrows. Resource saturation limits optimization flexibility, and service removal becomes necessary, reducing the impact of specific strategies. Consequently, at high loads, differences between methods diminish, as resource constraints dominate system behavior.

To complement the analysis of load distribution across clusters, we also computed the load imbalance ratio, defined as the ratio of the maximum to average CPU load across all clusters depicted in FIGURE 8(b). The load imbalance ratio compares the most loaded cluster to the average load across all clusters. In the low utilization range (1-3), B-L has the highest ratio, meaning one cluster is loaded more than twice the average. SD, Max, and Max-Min maintain lower ratios, indicating a fairer distribution of workload. In the medium range (4-6), differences between strategies decrease as demand forces the load to be spread more evenly. Even so, SD, Max, and Max-Min consistently show better balance than B-L and, to a lesser extent, B-C.

H. EXECUTION TIME RESULTS

Table 2 reports the execution time growth rates across increasing batch sizes for three methods: the ILP approach from [32], their Simulated Annealing (SA) heuristic, and our proposed ILP-based scheduling method. Each column shows the rate of execution time increase between consecutive batch sizes, providing insight into scalability. A lower growth rate indicates better scalability, suggesting the method can handle larger service requests without a significant rise in computational costs. The ILP from [32], designed to minimize total provisioning cost, exhibits exponential growth in execution time, e.g., from 3.92 (at 100 requests) to over

TABLE 2. Execution time for different problem size (service batch).

Num req	ILP [32]	SA [32]	ILP [proposed]
50	1	1	1
100	3.921	1.855	3.502
150	81.886	2.879	4.192
200	759.192	3.761	8.636

FIGURE 9. End-to-end service instantiation time based on different Batch size (number of services).

759 (at 200 requests) rendering it impractical for large-scale deployments. To mitigate this, the authors introduced a heuristic (SA), which achieves near-optimal results with significantly lower computation times.

Our approach shows a similar efficiency trend, maintaining growth rates closer to the SA heuristic rather than the original ILP. This indicates that our method strikes a favorable balance between solution optimality and execution efficiency, making it more suitable for large-scale service placement scenarios.

I. SYSTEM-LEVEL EVALUATION IN TESTBED

As proposed in Section III, the placement algorithm was implemented as a custom plugin for the Karmada scheduler. This subsection presents a system-level evaluation of the full architecture in a real testbed. Unlike the previous simulation-based results, this section evaluates the actual deployment time of services in a real federated testbed, capturing system-level overhead introduced during real execution. In this regard, we define end-to-end service instantiation time as the duration from service submission to the point when the corresponding pod is fully running in the cluster. While the simulation results focused on placement latency and CPU usage, this experiment assesses the responsiveness of the system under real deployment conditions. In this experiment, we have an operational environment EXTREME Testbed® of the CTTC, including Karmada control plane with three containerized Kubernetes clusters deployed using the Kind framework. Each cluster has 16 cores of available CPU, and the latency considered is 10, 20, and 50 ms. We selected cluster affinity and LB as benchmarks for this test. Cluster Affinity is a native Karmada policy that places services based on user-defined preferences.

FIGURE 9 shows the box plots analysis of the end-to-end service instantiation time for all the services in batch sizes 10, 15, 25, 50 for all repetitions. The affinity approach stands out with the narrowest interquartile range and the lowest

median, highlighting its faster service creation, while ILP and LB show a wider range with a higher median, hence higher service creation times. When comparing the ILP and LB approaches the maximum difference in time happened in batch size 10, with around 1 second and 7 milliseconds which will be reduced to zero in higher batch sizes, like 50. ILP performs better when the problem is large enough to benefit from global optimization, and the constraints start guiding the solver effectively.

VI. DISCUSSION

The evaluation highlights trade-offs between latency and CPU load across placement strategies. Latency-biased methods reduce service delay under light load but create CPU imbalance, while CPU-biased approaches improve load distribution at the cost of latency. Our ILP-based method with adaptive weighting strikes a more effective balance between these objectives. Under high load, all strategies converge in performance, as resource saturation enforces natural balancing. Load analysis confirms that metrics promoting perfect CPU balance yield more equitable utilization across clusters. The ILP solver scales moderately with batch size, remaining practical for large deployments. While heuristics execute faster, our results show that near-optimal placement is achievable with manageable overhead.

The real-world testbed evaluation validated deployment feasibility. The same ILP optimizer integrated into the Karmada control plane, and we measured end-to-end service instantiation time across federated clusters. Results confirm that global optimization can be integrated without degrading responsiveness, supporting latency-sensitive use cases such as autonomous driving, smart health, and critical infrastructure.

Architecture supports 5G/6G orchestration goals by combining centralized decision-making with distributed domains through a modular, plugin-based optimizer to fulfill the multi-domain coordination objective. Priority-based removal policies improve overload handling compared to naive approaches, and adaptive latency-CPU weighting offers flexibility for varied service profiles. The limitations include a focus on initial placement without post-deployment adaptation, a lack of service graph modeling, and the absence of dynamic traffic evaluation. Future work will address these gaps by enabling runtime migration, integration of real traffic patterns, and exploring learning-based optimizers.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed an optimal service placement strategy based on MILP integrated in a federated cluster environment, to simultaneously optimize the computational load balancing and end-to-end service latency. Through extensive simulations and benchmarking against baseline and heuristic strategies, several key achievements have been demonstrated. The system integrates an optimizer into the Karmada control plane to provide: (i) a multi-objective optimization framework for balancing latency and CPU utilization; and

(ii) an optimized service removal mechanism to guarantee feasibility under high-load conditions. The service placement problem was formally modeled as a MILP formulation to enable optimization across heterogeneous clusters. Several weighting strategies were studied for balancing latency and CPU metrics, including variance scaling (SD), Max-Min normalization, and Max normalization.

We presented the analysis of total allocated services under different CPU loads. In low CPU load that the system is not saturated and the results are not affected by any system stress, the proposed approach has $\sim 50\%$ average relative gaps with the B-L approach while this value is $\sim 78\%$ for the Balanced approach. The evaluation of maximum cluster capacity utilization showed that the ILP-based approach achieved consistently close results to the CPU-biased strategy. The ILP method maintained a balanced distribution even under high-demand CPU ranges. This result, together with unallocated service results, confirms that the ILP solution effectively avoids local resource bottlenecks and sustains service feasibility while preventing overload. In terms of computational efficiency, While the heuristic method in other studies remained faster at 3.761 seconds at 200 service requests, the proposed ILP ran only $\sim 2.3\times$ slower while delivering optimal solutions, thus making the approach both practical and computationally feasible for large-scale deployments.

Overall, our approach delivers a practical and effective solution for optimal service placement in federated clusters, achieving significant improvements in both latency and load balancing. The approach ensures optimal resource utilization, avoids bottlenecks, and maintains feasibility under varying loads, all while remaining computationally feasible for large-scale scenarios.

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